

Supplementary Materials

This PDF file includes:

Table S1-S2

Figures S1-S4

Table S1. Model fit statistics and AICc index describing the relationship between universal predictors and bacterial diversity. AICc measures the relative goodness of fit of a given model; the lower its value, the more likely it is that this model is correct. Two models with a Δ AICc value > 2 are considered to be substantially different. When the two models have similar AICc values, the most parsimonious solution (linear) is selected.

Biome	Predictor	Model	R ²	P	AICc	Δ AICc	Selected model	
Arid	pH	Linear	0.33	<0.001	1187.57	0.00	✓	
		Quadratic	0.34	<0.001	1188.70	1.13		
	Soil C	Linear	0.30	<0.001	1191.15	4.12		
		Quadratic	0.35	<0.001	1187.03	0.00	✓	
Temperate	UV light	Linear	0.02	0.215	1440.22	6.73		
		Quadratic	0.10	0.006	1433.49	0.00	✓	
	pH	Linear	0.33	<0.001	1187.57	0.00	✓	
		Quadratic	0.34	<0.001	1188.70	1.13		
	Soil C	Linear	0.30	<0.001	1191.15	4.12		
		Quadratic	0.35	<0.001	1187.03	0.00	✓	
	Continental	UV light	Linear	0.01	0.515	1219.88	12.16	
			Quadratic	0.17	<0.001	1207.72	0.00	✓
pH		Linear	0.42	<0.001	589.36	6.82		
		Quadratic	0.54	<0.001	582.54	0.00	✓	
Global	Soil C	Linear	0.16	0.011	604.40	0.00	✓	
		Quadratic	0.16	0.041	606.87	2.47		
	UV light	Linear	0.01	0.465	610.75	8.13		
		Quadratic	0.24	0.005	602.62	0.00	✓	
	pH	Linear	0.33	<0.001	3438.46	27.51		
		Quadratic	0.41	<0.001	3410.95	0.00	✓	
		Soil C	Linear	0.18	<0.001	3486.57	0.00	✓
			Quadratic	0.19	<0.001	3486.59	0.02	
UV light	Linear	0.00	0.575	3532.85	27.49			
	Quadratic	0.12	<0.001	3505.37	0.00	✓		

Table S2. Standardized significant direct effects and correlations not plotted at the SEM from Fig. 4.

Parameter			Estimate	P
UV light	←	Distance Equator	-0.96	< 0.001
Grasslands	←	Distance Equator	-0.85	< 0.001
UV light ²	←	Distance Equator	-0.95	< 0.001
Forests	←	Longitude	0.54	< 0.001
Grasslands	←	Longitude	-0.36	< 0.001
UV light ²	←	Longitude	-0.14	< 0.001
Soil pH	←	Longitude	0.38	< 0.001
Bacterial richness	←	Distance Equator	-0.50	0.004
Soil C	←	Longitude	-0.25	0.011
UV light	←	Longitude	-0.05	0.022
Soil pH	↔	UV light ²	-0.20	0.004
Soil pH ²	↔	UV light ²	-0.20	0.001
Soil pH	↔	Soil C _	-0.25	< 0.001

Figure S1. Bacterial community composition across arid, continental and temperate climates.

Figure S2. A priori structural equation model including direct and indirect effects of the universal predictors on bacterial alpha diversity.

Figure S3. Relationship between main climatic predictors and alpha diversity of bacterial communities across three globally distributed biomes.